

PROTECTIVE EFFECT OF DAPANSUTRILE AGAINST METHOTREXATE-INDUCED TESTICULAR TOXICITY IN RATS

Haider H. Motlak¹, Mahmoud Elshal¹, Marwa S. Serrya^{1*}

¹Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt.

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*Corresponding Author

Marwa S. Serrya*

Department of Pharmacology and
Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy,
Mansoura University, Mansoura,
Egypt.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Methotrexate (MTX) is a widely used therapy for the treatment of malignancies and autoimmune diseases; however, its use is limited by adverse effects such as testicular toxicity and impairment of male fertility. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate the protective effect of dapansutril (DAPA) against methotrexate (MTX)-induced testicular toxicity in rats. **Methods:** Twenty-four adult male rats were divided into four groups: control, MTX, MTX + DAPA (10 mg/kg), and MTX + DAPA (20 mg/kg). Testicular toxicity was first assessed by measuring relative testicular weight, sperm count, and sperm viability, in addition to histopathological examination of testicular tissue. **Results:** Administration of MTX resulted in a non-significant decrease in relative testicular weight; however, it caused a significant reduction in sperm count and viability. In addition, marked histopathological alterations were observed,

including degeneration of seminiferous tubules and disruption of spermatogenesis. Co-administration of DAPA with MTX produced a mild, dose-dependent improvement, where DAPA-treated groups showed a significant recovery in sperm parameters and partial restoration of testicular histoarchitecture. **Conclusion:** DAPA effectively attenuated MTX-induced testicular toxicity, preserving both testicular structure and function in a mild, dose-dependent manner. These findings suggest its potential role as a protective agent against chemotherapy-induced reproductive toxicity.

KEYWORDS: Dapansutril; Methotrexate; Testicular toxicity; Spermatogenesis; Sperm count; Sperm viability; Histopathology; Rat model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Methotrexate (MTX) is one of the most used widely as an antifolate drug. Also, it has a central role in treating of several malignancies and many autoimmune disorders. In spite of the fact that it is a widely used for its therapeutic efficacy, MTX is also associated with a spectrum of adverse effects which may limit its clinical use. Among the widely seen limitations; the reproductive intoxication may represent a large concern particularly in males, where MTX has been seen in many reports as an agent that could have impaired testicular function and compromise of fertility.^[1,2]

The testis is a highly specialized organ which is highly characterized by continuous divisions of cells and high differentiation throughout the seminiferous tubules of the testis. This dynamic process makes it particularly susceptible to many agents that are cytotoxic in nature, particularly MTX. In previous studies it was shown that MTX may have been able to disrupt the process of spermatogenesis which led to reductions in sperm count and viability, in addition to damage of structural nature to these seminiferous tubules. Also, the histopathological changes that are common and which include degeneration of germinal epithelium, sloughing of germ cells, atrophy of the tubules, and the appearance of multinucleated spermatogenic giant cells, all of which contribute to impaired reproductive capacity of the biological system.^[3-5]

Keeping in mind the clinical importance of retaining the male fertility, it is important and there is growing interest in identifying which agents that can lessen or reduce the toxicity of MTX on testis. In this regard, Dapansutril (DAPA) has been emerging as a compound of possible therapeutic value to treat and prevent toxicity of such type. Dapansutril is a small molecule that has been investigated in various experimental procedures for its ability to change responses that are inflammatory in nature. But at the same time, its potential protective effects against drug induced toxicity in testis has not been widely explored or studied.^[6-8]

The present study was designed to study and evaluate the protective effect of dapansutril against the potential testicular toxicity induced by MTX in rat. This goal was achieved by studying some important indicators of functions of normal testis such as relative testis weight,

the sperm count, and eventually the sperm viability, added to thorough histopathological examination of the tissues. By linking functional and structural indicators, this current study aims to provide a thorough evaluation of the potential role of dapansutril in keeping the testis normality under conditions of MTX induced injury.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Animals

Twenty-Four adult male Sprague–Dawley rats (170-230 g) were obtained from VACSERA (Giza, Egypt). Animals were housed under standard laboratory conditions at 25 ± 2 °C with a 12-hour light/dark cycle and had free access to food and water throughout the experimental period. All experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the guidelines approved by the Mansoura University Animal Care and Use Committee (MU-ACUC; Protocol No.: PHARM.MS.24.09.114).

2.2 Drugs and chemicals

Methotrexate (MTX; Unitrexate® 50 mg/2 mL) was obtained from Hikma Pharmaceuticals (Amman, Jordan). Dapansutril (DAPA) powder was purchased from HEOWNS (Tianjin, China) and freshly prepared in 0.9% normal saline prior to administration. Secobarbital sodium, obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (MA, USA), was dissolved in normal saline and used for anesthesia. All other reagents and chemicals were of analytical grade.

2.3 Experimental design

Animals were randomly divided into four experimental groups (n = 6 per group):

Control group: Received normal saline

MTX group: Received methotrexate to induce testicular toxicity

MTX+DAPA 10 group: Received methotrexate and low-dose dapansutril

MTX+DAPA 20 group: Received methotrexate and high-dose dapansutril

Methotrexate was administered as a single intraperitoneal dose (commonly 20 mg/kg) [9] to induce testicular injury. Dapansutril was administered orally once daily for 7 consecutive days at two different dose levels (e.g., 10 and 20 mg/kg).^[10]

2.4 Measurement of Relative Testis Weight

At the end of the experimental period, animals were sacrificed, and both testes were carefully excised, cleared of surrounding tissues, and weighed.

Relative testis weight was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{Relative testis weight} = \frac{\text{testis weight (g)}}{\text{final body weight (g)}}$$

2.5. Sperm Analysis

2.5.1. Sperm Count

Sperm count was determined using epididymal sperm samples by taking 50 μL of sperm suspension and dilute it with 950 μL normal saline (i.e. a 1:20 dilution). Counting was performed using a hemocytometer under light microscopy at 400 \times magnification. Results were expressed as million sperm per millilitre.^[11,12]

2.5.2. Sperm Viability

The rat's epididymal sperms were incubated at a temperature of 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a time of about 15-30 minutes in order to ensure proper sperm dispersion. Afterward, sperm viabilities were evaluated at 60-minute intervals for 3 hours (i.e. at hours 1, 2, and 3) using light microscopy to monitor motility and survival.^[11,12]

2.6. Histopathological Examination

The rats' testis tissues were then, immediately after collection, fixed in Davidson's solution (347 ml deionized water, 111 ml/l 100 % acetic acid, 320 ml/l 99 % ethanol and 222 ml/l formalin-solution 10 % phosphate buffered), then embedded in paraffin finally then sectioned into 4-5 μm thickness.

Afterward processed sections were subjected to staining with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and examined using a light microscopy for any possible histopathological changes in seminiferous tubules, germinal epithelium, depletion of spermatogenic cells, tubular atrophy, interstitial edema, Leydig cell alterations, and vascular congestion.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

The data of the study were all expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) which is followed by Tukey multiple comparison post hoc test were also employed in the statistical analysis of the study. On the other hand, Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's post hoc test was used for evaluating the histopathological changes. A value of $P < 0.05$ was chosen to consider a statistically

significant difference. All statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism software (version 9.0, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Effect of Dapansutrile on Relative Testis Weight

No significant difference in relative testis weight was observed among the experimental groups. MTX administration did not produce a noticeable change compared to the control group. Similarly, treatment with DAPA, did not significantly affect relative testis weight. The values in the MTX + DAPA 10 mg/kg and MTX+ DAPA 20mg/kg groups were comparable to both control and MTX groups (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Effect of DAPA on relative testis weight (testis weight/body weight ratio) in methotrexate-induced testicular toxicity. Data are expressed as mean ± SEM.

3.2. Effect of Dapansutrile on Sperm Count

MTX administration significantly decreased sperm count compared to the control group, indicating impaired spermatogenesis. In the combined treatment groups, DAPA significantly ameliorated the MTX-induced reduction in sperm count. The low-dose DAPA group demonstrated moderate improvement, whereas the high-dose DAPA group exhibited a more pronounced restoration of sperm count toward normal levels (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of Dapansutrile on sperm count (million/mL) in methotrexate-induced testicular toxicity. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM. * and # significant difference compared to the control and MTX groups, respectively.

3.3. Effect of Dapansutrile on Sperm Viability

Sperm viability was markedly reduced in the MTX-treated group compared to the control group. Co-treatment with DAPA significantly improved sperm viability at both dose levels compared to the MTX group. However, no significant difference was observed between the low-dose and high-dose DAPA groups. Both treatment groups showed partial restoration of sperm viability toward control values (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Effect of Dapansutrile on sperm viability at different time intervals in methotrexate (MTX)-induced testicular toxicity. (A) Sperm viability after 1 hour, (B)

Sperm viability after 2 hours, (C) Sperm viability after 3 hours. * and # significant difference compared to the control and MTX groups, respectively.

3.4. Histopathological Findings

The Histopathological examination of testis tissues has shown a well-preserved architecture in the control group (Figure 4 A and B) of the rats where the seminiferous tubules were shown to be regularly in good arrangement and were lined by an intact and regular germinal epithelium thus exhibiting a complete spermatogenic activity with many spermatozoa in the lumen. Also, normal interstitial spaces containing Leydig cells were observed in the testis.

Conversely, the MTX group (Figure 4 C and D) of rats which were treated with MTX used dose, has been shown to have been severely structural damaged where the damage was characterized by shrinking in the tubules and irregularities in these seminiferous tubules alongside of degeneration and the necrosis of the tubular epithelium. Also, extensive sloughing of germ cells into the lumen. Added to that, features were seen such as the nuclear pyknosis, the cytoplasmic vacuolization, oligospermia, and the presence of multinucleated spermatogenic giant cells, alongside with interstitial spaces widening.

The treatment of combination of DAPA with MTX has resulted in the improvement in testis histology in a dose dependent way. The MTX+DAPA 10 group (Figure 4 E and F) showed a partial recovery accompanied with a relatively preserved tubular structure. However, a mild Sertoli cell vacuolation accompanied by a slight interstitial expansion. In the other hand, the MTX+DAPA 20 group (Figure 4 G and H) exhibited an almost a complete regaining of normal testicular architecture, including regular seminiferous tubules, active spermatogenesis, and finally normal interstitial tissue.

Figure 4: Representative H&E-stained testicular sections showing the protective effect of dapansutrile against methotrexate (MTX)-induced toxicity.

Control group (A, B) exhibits normal seminiferous tubules with intact germinal epithelium and active spermatogenesis. MTX group (C, D) shows severe alterations, including shrunken and irregular tubules, tubular epithelial degeneration and necrosis (thin arrows), germ cell sloughing, nuclear pyknosis, vacuolization, oligospermia, multinucleated giant cells (curved arrow), and widened interstitial spaces.

MTX+DAPA 10 group (E, F) shows partial improvement with mild Sertoli cell vacuolation (arrowheads) and slight interstitial widening, whereas MTX+DAPA 20 group (G, H) demonstrates near-normal architecture with restored spermatogenesis.

Images were captured at $\times 100$ (scale bar = 100 μm) and $\times 400$ (scale bar = 50 μm).

4. DISCUSSION

Our study demonstrated that methotrexate (MTX) administration induced significant testicular injury and toxicity in rats. Although no significant change was observed in the relative testis weight, marked reductions in sperm count and viability were detected, accompanied by pronounced histopathological alterations. Collectively, these findings indicate impairment of both the structural integrity and functional capacity of the testes.^[6,13]

The significant deterioration in sperm parameters, including reduced sperm count and viability, suggests impaired spermatogenesis and diminished sperm quality [14,15]. These functional impairments were further confirmed by histopathological findings, which showed degeneration of seminiferous tubules, sloughing of germ cells, and the presence of multinucleated spermatogenic giant cells. Collectively, these alterations indicate disrupted spermatogenic activity [16]. On the other hand, co-administration of DAPA with MTX exerted protective effects across the evaluated parameters in a mildly dose-dependent manner. The observed improvements in sperm count and viability suggest partial recovery of spermatogenic function. These resulted functional improvements were in agreement with the histopathological findings. The group treated the low dose of DAPA showed partial recovery, with relatively preserved seminiferous tubule integrity, although mild structural alterations were still observed. In contrast, the high DAPA dose treated group demonstrated near-complete restoration of normal testicular architecture, including well-organized seminiferous tubules and active spermatogenesis. The strong concordance between functional parameters (sperm count and viability) and histopathological findings further supports the protective effect of DAPA. Overall, the results of this study indicate that DAPA effectively attenuates

MTX-induced testicular toxicity in rats in a mildly dose-dependent manner, thereby preserving both testicular structure and spermatogenic function.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, methotrexate (MTX) induces significant testicular toxicity, as evidenced by impaired sperm count and viability, along with pronounced histopathological damage, despite the absence of marked changes in relative testis weight. Co-administration of dapansutril (DAPA) effectively attenuated these alterations in a mildly dose-dependent manner, with the higher dose achieving near-complete restoration of testicular structure and function. Collectively, these findings indicate that DAPA exerts a protective effect against MTX-induced testicular injury and preserves spermatogenic activity.

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